

Open Journal of Radiology and Medical Imaging

Opinion

ISSN : 2583-1534

Open Access

Academic radiology degrees in the British educational system

Abdulwahab Alahmari

Radiology Specialist, Radiology Department, Al-Namas General Hospital, Ministry of Health, Al-Namas City, Saudi Arabia

***Corresponding Author:** Abdulwahab Alahmari, Radiology Specialist, Radiology Department, Al-Namas General Hospital, Ministry of Health, Al-Namas City, Saudi Arabia, Tel: +966562428716; Email: afaa99@hotmail.co.uk

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9959-830X

Received Date: Nov 16, 2021 / **Accepted Date:** Nov 17, 2021 / **Published Date:** Nov 18, 2021

Abstract

The aim of this paper is to describe some important academic degrees in radiology to make it a reference paper for students and applicants for degrees in radiology. Furthermore, to highlight some degrees in radiology many people are unfamiliar with these degrees.

Keywords: Radiology; Educational System; Academic Degrees; Taught Degree; Research Degree; Honorary Degree

Cite this article as: Abdulwahab Alahmari. 2021. Academic radiology degrees in the British educational system. O J Radio Med Img. 4: 57-59.

Copyright: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited. Copyright © 2021; Abdulwahab Alahmari

Introduction

The academic degrees in Radiology according to the British educational system started with the entry basic degree in Radiology and ended up with the honorary degree see (Diagram 1). Some of these degrees are offered for radiographers and some for Radiologists.

B.Sc. in Radiology

Bachelor's degree of science is the basic degree in the field and it could have different degree's names like Bachelor of Health Science (BHSc, BHSc, B.H.S, BHS, BHlthSc), Bachelor of Medical science (BMSc BMedSci, BMedSc, BSc (Med), BMSc), or other names and the specialty name can vary like radiography, medical imaging, diagnostic imaging, radiology, etc. it contains taught modules and

research project in some university or a dissertation. its 3-4 years long based on the university.

PgCert in Radiology

Post-graduate certificate is a taught degree after a bachelor degree. It has the most accredited post-baccalaureate program by the HCPC. it is usually a one-year-long program in a full-time study or less. It can be abbreviated as PGCert, PgCert, PG Cert, PGC, or PgC.

PgDip in Radiology

Post-graduate diploma is a taught degree after a PgCert. It is the second most accredited post-baccalaureate program by the HCPC. It is usually a one-year-long program in a full-time study or less. It can be abbreviated PGDip - PgDip, PG Dip, PGD, or PgD.

M.Sc. in Radiology

Master's degree of science is an advanced (higher education) and more specialized degree in one subspecialty like MRI for example. This degree allows to study a Ph.D. in the same specialization. This is a taught program that contains studying modules and a dissertation or a thesis. This is a 1 or 2 year-long program in a full-time study based on the university. The program is combination of PgCert, PgDip, and M.Sc.

MDRad

Master's degree in Diagnostic Imaging which allows a bachelor degree graduate from another field to join radiology field. This is an integrated master's program which means (a bachelor's degree in two years and a master's degree in two years). This is a 4 year-long program in a full-time study.

MPhil in Radiology

Master of Philosophy is a research degree that has no taught modules. This degree could be a part of a Ph.D. program. For example, a Ph.D. student did not make a doctorate level research, he/she will be awarded an MPhil in Radiology. As well, it could be a separate degree to allow B.Sc. graduate to study a Ph.D. degree and jump immediately to research. Usually, a one-year program in a full-time study and it could be longer.

MD in Radiology

Medical doctorate is a research degree designed for Radiologists to allow them to study a specific topic. This is a two-year-long program in a full-time study. The admission required condition is to have an M.B.B.S, MB ChB, BMBS, MB BCh, MB BChir or BM BCh (i.e., medicine bachelor and bachelor of surgery). This degree is different than the American M.D. degree.

Ph.D. (honoris causa h.c.) in Radiology

The Ph.D. h.c. is an honorary degree that can't be applied for it and honoris causa means ("for sake of the honour"). These degrees are not considered similar to degrees owned by academic process. Anyone who wins an honorary Ph.D. can't put "Dr." before his/her name, but the abbreviation with parentheses "h.c." can be used post-nominal. It can be listed on the curriculum vitae. Socially, it's not acceptable to use the title Dr. before the name if someone wins an honorary degree. In general, do not use the title, except in formal corresponding with the issuing university and when the issuing university addresses the winner, they will use the title "Dr.h.c." or "Dr.(h.c.)". These degrees can be withdrawn from the recipient if proven not to be fit for the honorary degree. Some university offer an honorary master's degree (less common), a Ph.D., a fellowship, or a Doctor of the University degree to distinguish a regular Ph.D. from an honorary Ph.D. This honorary Ph.D. degree is different than a D.Sc. This degree has no examinations, research, or taught subjects, but it's an award. These degrees have been associated with donation of money in some universities and strong connection with the faculty members.

Ph.D. or DPhil in Radiology

Doctor of Philosophy is a research degree and has no taught modules. Both Ph.D. and DPhil are the same, but oxford university uses DPhil instead of Ph.D. Both are three-year-long programs in a full-time study. This is one of the highest academic degrees which is very specialized in one topic.

D.Sc. in Radiology

Doctor of science is more an honorary degree. This degree is higher than the Ph.D. This degree can be applied for in some universities, while in some other university, they give this degree as an award for specific individuals. This degree is different from the American D.Sc. degree.

Diagram 1: This diagram shows different paths to reach the highest qualification level.